

RESEARCH AND EXECUTIVE
TRAINING CENTER IN HEALTH
ADMINISTRATION

UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence Award

Report 2018-2025

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1. Avant-garde value-based health services

1.1. UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence Award: Recognition of meaningful change

The UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence program was developed by Abbott in collaboration with world-leading professional societies, institutions, and associations in the fields of healthcare, economics, and quality to **inspire and foster worldwide healthcare excellence**.

With the aim of rewarding and celebrating best practices in the innovation of healthcare delivery, the program hosts an annual award. Participants are required to submit real-world evidence with a solid collaborative approach, involving at least three disciplines with the aim of solving a care gap or achieving a common goal. Judges are seeking **avant-garde, multidisciplinary, actionable, and scalable** solutions that generate **meaningful, immediate, and long-term impact** to value-based health services delivery.

Over 45 international professionals from partners organizations, with a shared vision of the needs and trajectories of healthcare, evaluate interdisciplinary candidates according to multidimensional key performance indicators (KPIs). Abbott is the sponsor of the award but does not have any role in the scoring process. Judges are focused on the measurable impact of clinical care initiatives on patients, clinicians, health systems/administrations, and payers.

In its history the award, from 2018 to 2025, hundreds of applications have been submitted worldwide, with only 85 being recognized for “excellence” (Figure 1). Award winning care initiatives demonstrate strength in cutting-edge approaches to solve problems in innovative ways for measurable impact, fostering unity across teams and disciplines.

Figure 1 - Geographical origin of the winning care initiatives (2018-2025)

1.2. Actionable value-based healthcare for excellence in health services delivery

The paradigm of value-based healthcare (VBH) was developed in 2006 by Porter and Teisberg and helped drawing back attention on the measurement of outcomes. It also contributed to making the necessary changes to structurally and systematically improve the performance of health systems and organizations. Porter and Teisberg (2006) proposed strategic agenda for value transformation consists of six elements: 1) work in integrated practice units that provide patient-centered care, 2) measure outcomes and costs for every patient, 3) move to bundled payments for care cycles, 4) integrate care delivery systems, 5) expand geographic reach to serve patients over a wide geographic area, and 6) build an enabling information technology platform that supports integrated, multidisciplinary care.

Many of the problems in today's healthcare – including over- or under-treatment, over- or under-diagnosed conditions, uncontrolled costs and budgets, errors in medical practice, and ineffectively distributed incentives – can be addressed through the concepts, practices, and tools of value-based healthcare. To date, however, value-based healthcare implementation has been primarily discussed in technical term of measurements, organizational structure, and competition. Change management practices have nevertheless repeatedly showed that a true shift from volume to patient value requires a change in culture and a different way of working of healthcare professionals.

Many healthcare providers are now working on the implementation of value-based healthcare by focusing on the measurement of outcomes. Organizations that have succeeded in measuring outcomes, however, are not widely disseminated in ways that improve service delivery and ensure evolution to become value-based care providers. To move from theory to practice, health organizations need best practices, clear direction, and actionable guidance.

It is within this context that the UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence award was launched.

1.3. How and why UNIVANTS enhances value-based healthcare

Health systems and organizations face an increasingly complex and complicated context, which can be explained by two main reasons.

The first reason is the current trends in disease and care patterns. Health systems have faced a varying patient epidemiology caused by more critical and frail patients. Care patterns are also changing, with new therapeutic opportunities emerging thanks to novel technology and enhanced technical skills. There has also been a focus on optimizing patient flow logistics and quality of care designed by specific pathways, improving patient journey and experience, adopting evidence-based medicine, and focusing on outcomes assessed through specific metrics. While these changes are leading to positive patient outcomes, they are complex to introduce and implement.

The second reason is the Volatile, Uncertain, Complex and Ambiguous (VUCA) environment. VUCA environment means that health systems and organizations face several – often opposed – pressures (political, societal, professional, mediatic, etc.), while undergoing major transformation catalyzed by disruptive innovation such as artificial intelligence, robots, precision medicine, and regenerative medicine.

In this light, health organizations and systems must pay greater attention to changes that generate innovation and value in service delivery.

Best practices and insights derived and/or associated with the UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence program can guide and present actions that health organizations can implement to transform into value-based outcomes.

Actions that have meaningful and sustainable impacts on four major areas of value generation in health:

- a) **Focus on patient-centeredness and experience:** reorganize care on the conditions of the patient, promote the integration of specialties and professionals, and abolish the organization in silos.
- b) **Pay for value:** adopt payment systems that incentivize cost reduction through more prudent spending and improve health by enhancing the quality of stay at the healthcare facility.
- c) **Buy for value and value-based innovation:** conduct cost analyses to understand the value of the interventions delivered in view of the health outcomes achieved. This means using real-life health technology assessments for decision-making and cost-quality algorithms for purchasing.
- d) **Value-based people management:** Engaging professionals are fundamental to achieving better performance. Generating skill mix, task shifting, multidisciplinary and multi-professional work is of paramount importance. Integrating engaged professionals, empowered patients and committed managers is what can help health organizations to make the leap to the next value level.

Integrated clinical care initiatives recognized by UNIVANTS are drivers to improve one or more of the above areas, through specific impact dimensions illustrated in the following section.

1.4. UNIVANTS is evidence-based with meaningful impact

Based on the principles and ambitions described above, the UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence award recognizes health organizations and their teams who collaborate across disciplines and professions to transform healthcare delivery and ultimately improve patient lives. **UNIVANTS is a driver for VBH as it recognizes and promotes valued best practices of health organizations that are innovating and transforming their care delivery according to value-based principles.**

Seven important dimensions can be connected with the improvements and innovations related to the best practices from UNIVANTS. Those dimensions are listed here below:

- 1) Improving systems and safety standards: optimizing logistics and adopting improved and standardized quality systems to increase the output, efficiency, and quality of care.
- 2) Multidisciplinary and multi-professional teams: this horizontal and transversal recipe focuses on teamwork and its capacity to dramatically improve the appropriateness of decision-making and capacity to steer clinical governance.
- 3) Less for more: Improve processes to decrease the unnecessary use of resources that can then be reinvested into the health system.
- 4) Leading research with new tests and models for better results: adding new types of tests and integrating and embedding specific tests in the care pathway and clinical practice. Using new clinical models to improve diagnosis, therapy, test uptake, thus enhancing patient safety and experience.
- 5) New delivery models: to achieve better patient safety, improve outcomes and performance and increase efficiency and productivity.
- 6) Better communication for stronger impact: Using better communication, networking, and marketing strategies to involve citizens, companies, and organizations to increase the available resources in the laboratory and hospitals and decrease costs.
- 7) Synergizing health organizations, physicians, and patients to improve clinical governance: teamwork, co-production and shared decision-making generate best conditions to achieve greater value in service delivery.

In this light, each best practice recognized by the UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence program was assessed against Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that highlight benefits for the different stakeholders, thus generating measurable impacts and value-creation. Examples are shown on the next table.

MEASURABLE IMPACT		
Stakeholders	Description	Examples of Qualifying KPIs
Patient	This category can encompass either parts of or the entire population being served at your care facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced Length of Stay • Protected Patient Safety • Enhanced Patient Wellness • Decreased Mortality • Improved Patient Experience • Increased Patient Satisfaction • Decreased Wait Time
Clinician	This category can encompass specialized medical disciplines and/or all clinical staff involved with the direct care and treatment of the patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved Clinician Confidence • Reduced Clinician Uncertainty • Increased Clinician Satisfaction • Reduced Litigation Risk
Administration	This category can encompass any or all components of healthcare administration including leadership, management, public health systems, healthcare systems, hospitals, and hospital networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced Unnecessary Hospital Admissions • Enhanced Resource Utilization • Increased Reimbursement • Enhanced Reputation (Index, Ranking, Award) • Improved Staff Satisfaction • Improved Employee Engagement • Reduced Readmission Rates • Improved Quality
Payor	This category reflects beneficiaries and/or care providers outside of hospital systems such as trusts, insurance, reimbursement, and partner relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased Healthcare Costs • Mitigated Risks

1.5. The strategic role of Laboratory Medicine for VBH improvements

As illustrated in previous paragraphs, healthcare delivery models are undergoing a radical transformation to address the contemporary challenges and changes in population needs. Laboratory Medicine, with all its -omics, is pivotal in this paradigm change by re-designing traditional roles and fostering stronger collaborations across hospital departments.

Laboratories can become innovation hubs to experiment with new organizational models and approaches that catalyze systemic improvements across various healthcare dimensions. This transformation is particularly

evident across four key areas: Population Health Management, task-shifting and skill-mix, innovation processes, and business model reengineering.

1. **Population Health Management.** Providing critical data-driven insights and enabling advanced decision-making, laboratories' contribution is essential for effective population health management, supporting both individual patient care and public health initiatives. Through their analytical capabilities, they facilitate the identification of health risks, early diagnosis, and the implementation of personalized, minimally invasive treatment plans, as well as reinforce their position as key enablers of **precision medicine** and long-term health system sustainability. Beyond their technical functions, laboratories are increasingly integrated into broader care models that prioritize **patient-centered, proactive healthcare** solutions, particularly valuable in the management of chronic diseases, where continuous monitoring and tailored therapeutic strategies significantly improve patient outcomes. This requires close collaboration between laboratories and other medical specialties to ensure that diagnostic insights seamlessly align with comprehensive patient care pathways. Establishing multidisciplinary working groups and fostering continuous dialogue between professionals and healthcare structures not only enhances the coordination of care but also drives the development of innovative, patient-centric solutions that respond to the dynamic needs of modern healthcare.
2. **Task-shifting and skill-mix: Redefining roles.** Laboratories are in a unique position to drive innovations in workforce management by optimizing the skill mix and implementing task-shifting strategies. By redistributing responsibilities between physicians and technicians, laboratories can enhance efficiency by delegating routine tasks to qualified technical staff, allowing specialists to focus on more complex cases. This is in parallel with the growing use of technology and artificial intelligence to ease the workload of both professions. Additionally, task-shifting fosters professional development through cross-training and upskilling, ensuring workforce adaptability in a rapidly evolving healthcare landscape. This approach also supports the integration of laboratory professionals into interdisciplinary care teams, improving care coordination and consequently leading to better patient outcomes. In this way, task-shifting not only helps address workforce shortages but also strengthens the laboratory's capacity to deliver timely, accurate diagnostics and enhance healthcare outcomes.
3. **Innovation: Pioneering digital transformation.** As technological innovation accelerates, laboratory services are emerging as key players in the digital transformation of healthcare. The introduction of advanced technologies such as molecular diagnostics, genomic medicine, and remote monitoring is significantly reshaping clinical practice. Laboratories contribute to this transformation by leveraging digital tools like advanced data analytics, artificial intelligence, and telemedicine solutions, all of which enhance diagnostic accuracy. Additionally, these innovations improve patient access by enabling remote testing and real-time consultations, supporting patient-centered care. By adopting cutting-edge technologies, laboratories are not only improving diagnostic precision but also transforming the overall patient experience. As diagnostic capabilities continue to evolve, laboratories are becoming foundational to the clinical decision-making process, offering faster, more precise results that influence treatment choices and outcomes.
4. **Business model reengineering.** Laboratories serve a wide range of patient populations - both internal and external - and stakeholders (e.g., companies, prescribers, scientific associations), which require a dynamic and flexible approach to service delivery. Business model reengineering enables laboratories to maximize their impact by segmenting services to meet the specific needs of diverse patient groups, such as acute vs. chronic care, inpatient vs. outpatient services, and others. By implementing lean practices, laboratories can optimize processes, enhance efficiency, and reduce waste. Furthermore, fostering collaborative networks through innovative organizational models, such as public-private partnerships and regional laboratory networks, helps strengthen the healthcare ecosystem. Exploring new aggregation models allows for more agile and patient-centered service delivery: reengineering techniques, lean management, quality improvement, and accreditation becomes an exemplary application of enterprise modeling in healthcare. Physicians and laboratory technicians, as integral members of multidisciplinary teams, contribute to the development of new organizational structures, such as clinical service lines and focused units within hospitals and integrated delivery systems. These efforts support a flexible, collaborative approach that can be

tailored to local needs through various aggregation methods, including cooperatives, consortiums, and public-private networks.

Given the trajectories outlined and the strategic importance that the laboratory plays in this sector, it is important that decision makers and healthcare managers observe the scenarios in which they operate with new lenses. They must embrace a comprehensive, cross-sectoral perspective that emphasizes the integration of multiple disciplines, promotes cooperation across medical specialties to enhance innovation and supports a more holistic approach to patient care, and adopts flexible and scalable delivery and operational models.

Like UNIVANTS, all stakeholders involved in the healthcare of tomorrow (top and middle managers, clinicians, decision makers and more) will have to achieve multidisciplinary collaboration, understood as a 'unity of strategic vision', with an avant-garde approach.

UNITY + AVANT-GARDE = UNIVANTS
OF HEALTHCARE EXCELLENCE

2. Why a report on the UNIVANTS Award?

The Report 2018-2025 **frames and classifies** recognized best practices across all editions of the UNIVANTS Award, building upon the latest and emerging paradigms that are transforming the way we expect care services to be delivered. It intends to support the process of “naming and framing” necessary to position initiatives within the current debate and discourse on current healthcare trends and trajectories. Indeed, according to the methodology developed for the “UNIVANTS Award White Paper” ¹, care initiatives **related to the current narrative** should inspire the “new normal” of health services (value-based healthcare, population health management, patient-centricity, co-creation and co-production, “choosing wisely”, clinical services lines, task shifting and more) and best practices will be re-conceptualized and illustrated to maximize their potential to be replicated in other laboratories and healthcare organizations.

The aim of the Report is to provide laboratories and health organizations with a **“smart tool” to identify meaningful innovation** taking place in laboratories and healthcare organizations, as well as offer ample “food for thought” and actionable knowledge.

In conclusion, harmonization is needed to improve the scalability of the best practices. This Report develops a framework to enhance the learning experience as well as understanding which best practices fit best with reader needs. This will help the reader develop a deeper and clearer understanding of the “value” of the contributions made by the best practices of UNIVANTS, which serve as **benchmarks** and references for organizational change and innovation, significantly influencing the new normal in health services.

Below readers can find some of the questions the Report wants to answer in order to facilitate “learning from best practices”.

*How can effective multidisciplinary skills be **developed**?*

*How can the value of clinical competence of lab physicians within health services delivery be **enhanced**?*

*How can you **re-design** lab production processes to generate significant cost savings, increase safety, improve reliability etc.?*

*How can positive task-shifting and skill-mix among lab professionals be **generated**? How can “disruptive” technology **change** lab performance?*

¹ European Health Management Association (2020). Insights for value-based healthcare – Lessons from the UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence awards. Available at <https://ehma.org/app/uploads/2022/12/Lessons-from-the-UNIVANTS-for-Healthcare-Awards-November-2020.pdf>

3. In search of best practices

3.1. Naming

UNIVANTS awards analysis

To facilitate the identification, comparison, and study of best practices among UNIVANTS award-winning initiatives, a **classification framework** was developed based on a conceptual and methodological analysis of innovation patterns in laboratory and interdisciplinary healthcare.

Specifically, each best practice was examined based on **four critical elements** to allow a structured comparison of initiatives:

- **Dimension** – *thematic domain or area of intervention*. It defines the core field in which the initiative operates, whether clinical, organizational, technological, or strategic, thus shaping its objectives, methodology and expected impact.
- **Level** – *scope or extent to which the initiative generates impact*. It specifies whether the intervention targets the organization or system level, thus identifying the relative degree of impact expected to be observed.
- **Change focus** – *key strategies, mechanisms or tools adopted to drive transformation*. It identifies elements that activate the core ‘dimension’ and serve as operational enablers for measurable change and intended final improvements.
- **Final improvement** – *area of value creation or benefit achieved*. It reflects the area of advancement introduced by the initiative, thereby articulating results achieved.

This classification seeks to “name” clinical care initiatives and their contributions, providing a map of strategic insights on laboratory and interdisciplinary medicine. The analysis overall highlights how interdisciplinary collaboration across disciplines, often driven by laboratory medicine, can act as catalyst for healthcare transformation and innovation.

Dimension

This category allows for a granular understanding of how each award-winning initiative contributes to healthcare innovation, linking specific interventions to broader strategic actions. Specifically, initiatives were classified into eight dimensions as described below, each representing a distinct vector of value creation.

- **Avant-garde research**: initiative led by laboratories and research centers acting as incubators of innovation by generating, participating in, and steering pioneer initiatives. These initiatives contribute to the advancement of scientific knowledge by introducing novel concepts, methodologies or services in laboratory medicine and other healthcare disciplines. Avant-garde initiatives have the potential to disrupt or replace traditional service models, thus informing future clinical practices and healthcare policies.
- **Information and disease management**: initiative that develop solutions supporting and enabling data-driven decision-making processes and disease surveillance and monitoring. Building upon analytical and scientific capabilities of laboratories, these initiatives aim at integrating clinical information systems, predictive models, and algorithmic tools to support clinical and organizational improvement. On the one hand, they contribute to advancing chronic disease management, population health management, and precise and proactive healthcare delivery, on the other, to enhancing transparency, organizational efficiency and resource optimization.
- **Organizational transformation**: initiatives that drive systemic, structural, and procedural changes within healthcare organizations to enhance performance, quality, sustainability, and responsiveness to evolving healthcare needs. These initiatives encompass the redesign of care and managerial processes and definition of innovative governance models, reconfiguring the role of laboratories as strategic partner for transformation and change other than mere diagnostic provider.

- **Patient engagement:** initiatives adopt a patient-centered approach by encouraging the active participation of patients in their own care pathways. Through education initiatives, communication tools, shared decision-making processes and digital health solutions, these initiatives seek to foster patient empowerment and agency. The goal is the improvement of patient adherence to treatment, health outcomes, satisfaction, and alignment of care delivery with patient preferences and values.
- **Patient journey:** initiatives that improve the continuity, effectiveness and efficiency of patient pathways across multiple settings and stages of care. Through patient pathway re-engineering, improved coordination across healthcare actors and continuous performance monitoring, these initiatives aim at reducing care fragmentation, eliminating bottlenecks and redundancies, ensuring timely access to care and improving the overall patient experience.
- **Personalized medicine:** projects dedicated to the development and implementation of individualized care strategies. Utilizing genetic data, biomarkers, or other patient-specific variables, these initiatives aim to tailor diagnostics and therapeutics to patient characteristics. By enhancing diagnostic precision, therapeutic efficacy, and adaptive care, they thereby contribute to improved clinical outcomes.
- **Safety and risk management:** initiatives prioritizing patient safety and systematic management of clinical risks. These initiatives facilitate and improve the prevention of medical errors, implementation of risk management frameworks, early detection of adverse events, and enactment of robust safety protocols. They aim at embedding a culture of safety within healthcare organizations, thus enhancing the reliability and accountability of care delivery processes.
- **Workforce development:** initiatives address the capacity-building needs of healthcare professionals. Through structured and systematic training, interprofessional education and continuous professional development, these initiatives are intended to cultivate managerial and clinical skills and competences of the healthcare workforce, in alignment with evolving technologies and new care models. They are also focused on enhancing staff physical and mental well-being, resilience and retention, factors recognized as critical for successful healthcare innovations.

Level

This category informs the reader on the scale of impact of each clinical care initiative by identifying whether the innovation introduced transforms a specific health organization or the health system at a broader level. Specifically, projects were categorized as follows:

- **System level:** projects interventions bringing a system-wide impact beyond individual healthcare organizations and laboratories, driving improvements across the broader population. These initiatives typically involve multiple healthcare professionals, organizations, and settings, are regionally/nationally implemented and/or involve institutional actors.
- **Organization level:** initiatives interventions introducing improvements within a single institution or healthcare provider entity. These initiatives usually involve healthcare professionals within the same organization. It should be noted that, while being locally bounded, these initiatives may serve as pilots for broader transformation and can be scaled or adapted to other contexts.

Change focus

This category sheds light on how innovation is realized by identifying the tools, methodologies, strategies, and mechanisms enabling measurable changes in laboratories and healthcare organizations. Change focuses were classified as follows:

- **Automation and new technology:** this change focus refers to the implementation of hard technologies and automated systems (often algorithm-based) that transform diagnostic or operational procedures, replacing or augmenting manual processes. The adoption and integration of technological advancements is typically associated with improvements in diagnostic accuracy, efficiency, and consistency.

- **Digitalization:** it describes the implementation and adoption of soft technologies and digital systems facilitating the strategic use of data to optimize healthcare delivery. The digitalization of data flows and information systems, provider and patient interfaces and decision-support tools allow the management of data in a structured, standardized, and safe manner, thus enhancing data-based decision-making, care coordination, transparency, and accountability.
- **Communication:** it refers to the strategic improvement of communication flows between stakeholders, either internal (e.g., clinical teams, laboratories, ...) or external (e.g., patients, caregivers, public health institutions, ...). Strategies may include the establishment of interdisciplinary communication channels, the design of educational tools for patients, or the development of communication campaigns. This change focus fosters knowledge sharing, coordination, and trust among stakeholders of the healthcare sector.
- **Delivery models:** this focus includes the development and implementation of innovative care delivery frameworks redefining the organization, structuring or provision of healthcare services to extend their reach and responsiveness. These innovative models may include point-of-care testing models, mobile health units or enhanced patient tracing systems, frequently entailing the strategic repositioning of laboratory medicine within the care continuum. The aim is to improve accessibility and continuity of care.
- **Patient pathway re-engineering:** it describes the systematic redesign and optimization of clinical pathways across different care settings and disciplines with a holistic, multidisciplinary, and patient-centric approach. This change focus addresses clinical flows, care transitions and patient experience, targeting efficiency, timeliness, coordination, and quality of patient care.
- **Process and operations re-engineering:** it is related to the systematic redesign and optimization of internal workflows, organizational and operational processes within laboratories and healthcare organizations. It includes workflow standardization and innovation and aims at increasing efficiency, minimizing waste, and improving service quality.
- **Service integration:** this change focus describes the coordination and alignment of diagnostic, clinical and administrative services into cohesive and efficient systems, for example through cross-departmental or cross-institutional collaboration and shared digital infrastructures. By operating in synergy other than in silos, connected systems facilitate care continuity, ultimately improving quality and efficiency.
- **Standards and metrics:** it refers to the development and adoption of new or refined clinical and/or operations standards and protocols focused on quality and safety and coupled with the measurement of performance indicators. By allowing healthcare organizations to monitor, evaluate and improve their clinical and operational performance, the goal is to foster quality assurance, risk management, transparency, and continuous improvement.
- **Teams and skill-mix:** it focuses on the reshaping of healthcare teams' structure and composition, collaborative dynamics, and skills and competences. This may include the creation of multidisciplinary and multi-professional care teams, the strategic reconfiguration of roles and responsibilities, often through task-shifting, upskilling, or interprofessional training. The aim is to maximize human capital, and foster collaboration and adaptation of healthcare teams.

Through the analysis for each clinical care initiatives two key change focuses/drivers were identified, if relevant and used for its classification.

Final improvement

This category identifies the outcome or impact area that the clinical care initiative aims to improve, offering a structured and outcome-oriented lens for evaluating healthcare innovations introduced. Improvements were classified as follows:

- **Access:** initiatives expanding the availability and reach of healthcare services to ensure equitable access across geographic, socioeconomic, and demographic boundaries. This includes addressing gaps in availability, reducing disparities in service utilization, and extending inclusivity of care to marginalized, rural or underserved communities.

- **Appropriateness:** initiatives ensuring that healthcare interventions are aligned with clinical evidence, best practices, national and international guidelines, and individual patient needs. By avoiding the underuse or overuse of services and promoting evidence-based and personalized care, the final aim is to reduce unnecessary tests or treatments, deliver accurate diagnoses and increase adherence to guidelines.
- **Economic sustainability:** initiatives improving the financial viability and long-term affordability of healthcare services by optimizing cost-effectiveness and reducing unnecessary spending while delivering high quality and equitable care. By lowering costs, rationalizing resource allocation and improving financial resilience, it supports the long-term economic sustainability of health systems while ensuring the production of the greatest clinical, operational, and social value.
- **Outcome improvement:** initiatives enhancing clinical effectiveness and impact of interventions by ensuring intended health outcomes are achieved. Based on evidence-based practices and continuous performance assessment, it directly measures whether innovations actually translate into real-world health benefits for patients (e.g., higher survival rates, reduced hospitalization rates, improvement quality of life)
- **Efficiency and productivity:** initiatives maximizing the output of healthcare services and operations while minimizing waste, delays, and resource misuse. It includes the optimization of workflows, operational processes, labor utilization and clinical activities, in the end enhancing system current sustainability and responsiveness.
- **Patient experience:** initiatives improving how patients perceive and interact with the healthcare system throughout their care journey. By enhancing communication, personalization of care, emotional well-being and support, patient engagement and responsiveness to their needs and preferences, this area facilitates higher patient satisfaction, trust, treatment adherence, and health literacy.
- **Public health improvement:** initiatives strengthening population-level health through disease prevention, health promotion, early detection, and epidemiological surveillance. By supporting public health interventions and planning, it is focused on lowering disease burdens, improving community health outcomes, and strengthening health system resilience.
- **Quality:** initiatives ameliorating care services through high clinical, operational, and procedural standards. It ensures care delivery is effective, reliable, patient-centered, and consistent with high-level benchmarks and guidelines, fostering clinical excellence and health system robustness.
- **Safety:** initiatives preventing harm to patients and healthcare professionals during the provision of care by minimizing risks, errors and adverse events. It encompasses the identification, mitigation, and elimination of risks, errors, and adverse events across all phases of healthcare delivery, leading to fewer diagnostic and treatment errors, enhanced patient trust, and reduced legal risk.

Each clinical care initiative is categorized based on a primary and secondary area of benefit, if relevant, while recognizing that many also generate improvements across other domains.

3.2. Framing

The following matrix allows readers to visually connect each single project to the logical categories described above. Initiatives are listed in chronological order from 2025 to 2018, classified based on the dimension of focus, and divided by scope of impact (level). It should be noted that the inclusion of a clinical care initiative on one level rather than the other does not mean the initiative cannot be scalable at a wider level.

Titles of the clinical care initiatives were abbreviated by authors due to spatial constraints; bibliographic details of each initiative (title, institution, and country of reference) are listed in the section 'UNIVANTS Winners' with a numerical reference to short version titles.

Below is the legend of the icons used to describe “change focuses” and “final improvements”. Colored boxes into the matrix indicate the “change focuses” that activated the dimension and contributed to achieve results, as well as the “final improvements” generated by the initiative under analysis.

Figure 2 - Legend of icons

Figure 3 - Matrix of winners

D	L	PROJECT SHORT TITLE	CHANGE FOCUS			FINAL IMPROVEMENT									
Avant-garde research	Organization	Reduced hepatocellular carcinoma recurrence post liver transplant ⁽⁸⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Enhance the ability to identify macroprolactinemia ⁽⁷⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Improving emergency department flow and decreasing risk ⁽⁵⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Early Diagnosis of Acute Kidney Injury ⁽⁴⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Preventing Cardiovascular Disease ⁽⁴⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Reducing Post-Operative Complications in Cardiac Surgery ⁽³¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Increase Early Diagnosis of Liver Disease ⁽¹⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
	System	Improved Diagnostic Pathway for Hospitalized Acute Kidney Injury ⁽¹⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Simplifying the diagnosis of clostridioides difficile ⁽⁶⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Real-time donor screening for infectious disease ⁽⁶⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Improving the Safety of Mothers and Babies for Pre-eclampsia ⁽¹⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Identification of Familial Hypercholesterolemia ⁽¹²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										

D	L	PROJECT SHORT TITLE	CHANGE FOCUS			FINAL IMPROVEMENT																
Equity and inclusion	Org.	Increased Detection of Acute Myocardial Infarction in Women ⁽²³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Testing for sexually-transmitted and blood-borne infections ⁽⁷⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Maternal drug screening ⁽⁷¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Improving access to health services in vulnerable communities ⁽⁷²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Empowering women to eliminate cervical cancer ⁽⁶³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Surveillance for Hypertension, Diabetes and Chronic Kidney Disease ⁽³⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
Information and disease management	Organization	The Fiix project: Reducing anticoagulation variability and adverse patient outcomes ⁽⁸²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Enhanced discrimination of myocardial injury in a pediatric population ⁽⁴⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Personalized care for Heart Failure patients ⁽⁵³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Reduction of Inpatient Daily Blood Draws ⁽³⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
	System	Syphilis screening strategy for cost-effective and timely syphilis management ⁽⁸¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Timely Patient Communication of COVID-19 Status ⁽²⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Early Diagnosis and Improved Management of Patients with Diabetes ⁽⁴⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	
		Prenatal Care-A Clinical Laboratory Driven Initiative ⁽¹⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																	

D	L	PROJECT SHORT TITLE	CHANGE FOCUS			FINAL IMPROVEMENT									
Organizational transformation	Organization	Improved patient experiences and decreased patient length of stay in the ED ⁽⁷⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Strategic laboratory stewardship ⁽⁵⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Safe and informed population health management during the COVID-19 pandemic ⁽⁶²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Rapidly Improving Timeliness of Laboratory Test Results in an Acute Care Setting ⁽⁵¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Improved patient pathway for Multiple Myeloma ⁽⁴⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Enhanced Discovery of Unidentified Comorbidities and Diagnosis ⁽²⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Maximizing efficiency in the lab to save more lives through organ donation ⁽⁶⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
	System	System	Improving Morbidity and Mortality in Patients with Sepsis ⁽⁴⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Activation of Point-of-Care Testing in an Emerging Market ⁽³²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Collaborative Among Public and Private Sectors for SARS-CoV-2 Testing ⁽³⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Using Data, Innovation, and Collaboration to Support Better Patient Outcomes ⁽²⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Early Recognition and Management of Sepsis in the Emergency Department ⁽¹⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Troponin and Biomarkers on Ischemic Myocardial Injury and Surgical Care ⁽⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Expanded Investments in Laboratory Medicine ⁽⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									

D	L	PROJECT SHORT TITLE	CHANGE FOCUS			FINAL IMPROVEMENT														
Patient engagement	Org.	Detection of Cardiovascular Risk in Asymptomatic Blood Donors ⁽⁴⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION															
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS															
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS															
System		Improving Population Health Through Screening for Hepatitis C ⁽²⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION															
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS															
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS															
		Identification of HCV & HIV via Opt-Out ED Screening with Active Education ⁽³⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION															
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS															
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS															
		Increased Blood Donations Through Partnerships and Media Campaigns ⁽⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION															
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS															
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS															
Patient journey (1/2)	Organization (1/2)	ED Radiation Reduction for patients with suspected mild traumatic brain injury ⁽⁸⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION															
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS															
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS															
			Blood biomarker guided management of patients with suspected mild TBI ⁽⁸³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION														
				COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS														
				DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS														
			Reducing unnecessary CT scans in the emergency department ⁽⁶⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION														
				COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS														
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																
	Reducing unnecessary admissions associated with pediatric mononucleosis ⁽⁶⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																
		COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS																
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																
	Diagnostic pathway in the ED with suspected mild traumatic brain injury ⁽⁵⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																
		COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS																
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																
	Optimizing the care, safety, and wellness of patients with known diabetes ⁽⁴²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																
		COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS																
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																
	Renal Osteodystrophy Monitoring ⁽⁴¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																
		COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS																
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																
	New Chest Pain Pathway, Expedited by and for the COVID-19 Era ⁽³⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																
		COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS																
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																
	Early Detection and Management of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus ⁽³⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																
		COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS																
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																
	Improving Care and Overall Experience with Suspected Cardiovascular Diseases ⁽²⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION																
		COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS																
		DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS																

D	L	PROJECT SHORT TITLE	CHANGE FOCUS			FINAL IMPROVEMENT									
Patient journey (2/2)	Org. (2/2)	Pre-Surgical Biomarker Risk Assessment in Patients Undergoing Eye Surgery ⁽²⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Optimization of Heart Failure Management using Biomarkers ⁽⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Follow-up & treatment for patients with diabetes and chronic kidney disease ⁽⁷⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
	System	Early detection of metabolic dysfunction associated steatotic liver disease ⁽⁷⁶⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Empowering women's health-coronary risk ⁽⁶⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Improving the peri-operative elective pathway of people with diabetes ⁽⁶⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Sustained 97% optout HIV testing in the Emergency Department ⁽⁵²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
		Faecal Immunochemical Tests for patients with New Bowel Symptoms ⁽²⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
	Personalized medicine (1/2)	Organization	Reclassification and therapeutic changes for patients with diabetes ⁽⁷³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Detection and Management of Thyroid Dysfunction During Pregnancy ⁽¹⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Avoiding Insufficient Therapies and Overdosing with Co-Reporting eGFRs ⁽¹³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Personalized Antibiotic Therapy for Reduced Inappropriate Exposure ⁽¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			Integrated Clinical Care Strategy Improves Emergency Patient Flow ⁽³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
		(1/2)	Personalizing antibiotic therapy for enhanced safety eradication ⁽⁷⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									

D	L	PROJECT SHORT TITLE	CHANGE FOCUS			FINAL IMPROVEMENT									
Person. (2/2)	System (2/2)	Getting to zero harm in controlled substance prescribing ⁽⁵⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
		Optimizing and Standardizing ACS Patient Pathways ⁽²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
Safety and risk management	Organization	A noninvasive serologic model using an intelligent informatic solution ⁽⁵⁸⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
			Screening and establishing a COVID-19 convalescent plasma bank ⁽⁴³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
				COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS									
				DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS									
			Reducing Catastrophic Adverse Events in Patients with Hemorrhagic Shock ⁽³³⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
				COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS									
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
		Strategic SARS-CoV-2 Testing for Healthcare Workers and Patients ⁽³⁵⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
		Screening Programs for Safe, Back to Work Strategies during COVID-19 ⁽²²⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
		Improved Safety for Patients with Indeterminant Pulmonary Nodules ⁽¹⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
	System	The pathway to HCV elimination ⁽⁸⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
				DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS									
			Improved management of high LDL-C through EHR-directed algorithms ⁽⁷⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
				COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS									
				DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS									
			Early diagnosis of maternal cytomegalovirus ⁽⁶¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
		Improving COVID clinical and translational challenges ⁽⁵⁰⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
		Maintain High Quality Patient Care During the COVID-19 Pandemic ⁽²¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										
		Identifying Untreated Hepatitis B and Hepatitis C via Optout Screening Program in ED ⁽¹¹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION										
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS										
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS										

D	L	PROJECT SHORT TITLE	CHANGE FOCUS			FINAL IMPROVEMENT								
Workforce development	Org.	Improving Quality, Patient Care and Experience, While Lowering Costs ⁽⁹⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS									
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS									
	System	Enhanced staff satisfaction and resource utilization during the COVID-19 pandemic ⁽⁵⁷⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS									
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS									
		Improved Clinical Pathway for Diabetes in Hospitalized Patients ⁽⁴⁾	TECHNOLOGY	DIGITALIZATION	INTEGRATION									
			COMMUNICATION	PATHWAY	STANDARDS									
			DELIVERY	OPERATIONS	TEAMS									

4. Last glimpse

In this section, a final (over)view on the “figures” of the UNIVANTS award is provided for the reader interested in having the big picture of the areas of impact.

UNIVANTS does not have expected numbers of clinical care initiatives that can be recognized for each dimension of change focus. What is recognized is simply best in class based on what is meaningful and impactful according to the evidence-based criteria used by judges.

Therefore, any path that could be depicted in the flow of awarded best practices could be considered a mirror of what naturally is taking place within health systems worldwide as focus for innovation and transformation.

Not surprisingly, the change focuses most readily present are patient engagement, patient journey, personalized medicine, and organizational transformation.

Below are graphics that summarize the “classification” of awarded best practices, so that the reader can make their own reflections on them.

Figure 4 - Awarded best practices re-classified for main dimension: total and single year

Figure 5 - Awarded best practices re-classified for change focus: total and single year

Figure 6 - Awarded best practices re-classified for final improvement: total and single year

Figure 7 - Total awarded best practices re-classified for main dimension vs change focus or final improvement

HALL OF FAME: the UNIVANTS Winners

Below is a detailed list of all recognized best practices in chronological order that have received recognition through the UNIVANTS of Healthcare Excellence award program and were used to compile this Report. For each integrated clinical care initiative, the authors provide a summary to help readers quickly understand its contents.

2018

1. Personalized Antibiotic Therapy for Reduced Inappropriate Exposure to Antibiotics

Swedish Covenant Hospital
USA

An initiative at Swedish Covenant Hospital in Chicago aimed to reduce inappropriate antibiotic exposure. An integrated care team, including infectious disease specialists and pharmacy, implemented evidence-based procalcitonin criteria to optimize antibiotic management in the ICU. This led to a significant 23% reduction in antibiotic exposure, a 2.3-day decrease in hospital stay, and a \$2,759 reduction in cost per patient, ultimately improving overall patient outcomes.

2. Optimizing and Standardizing ACS Patient Pathways

Canterbury and the New Zealand Healthcare System
New Zealand

In Canterbury, New Zealand, an initiative optimized and standardized pathways for patients presenting to the Emergency Department with suspected Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS). An integrated team developed an Accelerated Diagnostic Pathway (ADP) using risk scores and biomarkers to enable safe and early discharge for low-risk patients. This approach positively impacted key performance indicators such as length of stay and has been successfully extended across New Zealand.

3. Integrated Clinical Care Strategy Improves Emergency Patient Flow

The Royal Wolverhampton NHS Trust
England

The Royal Wolverhampton NHS Trust in the UK implemented a multidisciplinary integrated care initiative to optimize pathways for suspected Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS) and address emergency department pressures. The initiative focused on identifying low-risk patients to facilitate a rapid discharge protocol. This reduced unnecessary admissions and positively impacted key performance indicators like reduced mean length of stay and healthcare costs.

4. Improved Clinical Pathway for Recognizing and Treating Diabetes in Hospitalized Patients

University Hospital Tübingen
Germany

At the University Hospital Tübingen in Germany, an improved clinical pathway addressed the under-recognition of diabetes in hospitalized patients. An integrated care team introduced universal HbA1c screening to identify previously undiagnosed diabetes. This led to more accurate prevalence recognition and optimized treatment pathways, aiming to improve outcomes and reduce the mean length of stay.

2019

5. Maximizing Patient Care and Reducing Mortality Through Expanded Investments in Laboratory Medicine Including a Comprehensive External Quality System

General Directorate of Allied Health Services Ministry of Health
Palestine

The Ministry of Health in Palestine implemented a comprehensive quality management system (QMS) in laboratory medicine. Laboratory quality is vital for patient outcomes but often neglected in developing countries. The three-year initiative included developing and implementing extensive quality assurance measures across over 200 health facilities. This partnership resulted in improved maternal and infant health, increased staff satisfaction, increased revenue, reduced risk, and led to ISO 15189 accreditation, improving quality and innovation within the healthcare system.

6. Increased Population Engagement, Enhanced Patient Experience, and Safe Blood Donations Through Strategic Partnerships and Targeted Media Campaigns

Dubai Health Authority
United Arab Emirates

The Dubai Health Authority (DHA) implemented a strategy using strategic partnerships and targeted media campaigns to increase blood donations. Access to blood products is crucial, but donations are limited, especially among young people. In 2015, donations were insufficient. An integrated care team launched a marketing campaign, "BE THE 1", to attract new donors, particularly the younger population. This led to a significant 37% increase in total donations, reduced healthcare costs, and improved physician satisfaction.

7. The Global Impact of Troponin and Biomarkers on Ischemic Myocardial Injury and Surgical Care

Hamilton Health Sciences/Population Health Research Institute Hamilton
Canada

Hamilton Health Sciences in Canada conducted a study on myocardial injury in patients undergoing non-cardiac surgery. Over 200 million non-cardiac surgeries occur globally annually, with over 1 million deaths within 30 days. The study used high-sensitivity cardiac troponin to establish myocardial injury's contribution to these deaths. A clinical and laboratory model was developed and implemented into clinical care to detect and predict major cardiac events. This partnership aims to improve the understanding and management of ischemic injury and support innovative investigation.

8. Optimization of Heart Failure Management using Biomarkers in Patients with Low Risk for Rehospitalization

University Medical Center Groningen
Netherlands

The University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG) in the Netherlands initiated an innovative program for heart failure patient follow-up. Heart failure has significant clinical impact and high costs, including readmissions. Biomarkers like galectin-3 can identify a proportion of patients discharged with low risk. These patients can benefit from less intensive follow-up, allowing individualized risk-based treatment to optimize resources and improve outcomes.

9. Improving Quality, Patient Care and Experience, While Lowering Costs Through Enhanced Laboratory Stewardship

Cleveland Clinic
USA

Cleveland Clinic in Ohio, USA, has a Laboratory Stewardship Committee of clinicians, pathologists, administrators, and nurses working to optimize laboratory test utilization. The goal is to promote best practices, improve patient care, and reduce costs. Activities include reducing unnecessary phlebotomies and tests and promoting judicious molecular testing. Ten interventions since 2011 have been integrated. This has prevented 160,072 unnecessary tests and saved \$5,060,066, while improving quality, patient care, and experience.

10. Improving Clinical and Quality Outcomes for Prenatal Care - A Clinical Laboratory Driven Initiative

TriCore Reference Laboratories
USA

TriCore Reference Laboratories in New Mexico, USA, collaborated with a Managed Care Organization (MCO) for a statewide program to improve prenatal care. New Mexico ranks low in adequate prenatal care and pre-term births. Over 11 months, the lab provided actionable information to MCO care coordinators for over 1,300 pregnancies. Based on longitudinal lab results, insights aimed to improve prenatal care timeliness, identify high-risk births in real-time, close care gaps, and improve outcomes. The targeted intervention resulted in improved performance measures and birth outcomes.

11. Identifying Untreated Hepatitis B and Hepatitis C via Opt-out Screening Program in Urban ED Settings

Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust and Viapath Pathology Analytics
England

Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust and Viapath Pathology Analytics, UK, implemented opt-out screening for untreated HBV and HCV in urban emergency departments (ED). HBV and HCV are major public health issues, often unrecognized. A collaborative project increased test acceptance from 0-1% to over 70%. This resulted in a 26% and 15% increase in diagnosing previously unknown HBV and HCV infections. It has reduced further disease progression and led to an estimated 33% annual saving per patient.

12. FH ALERT: Identification of Patients with Familial Hypercholesterolemia (FH) by using the Expertise and Resources of the Clinical Laboratory

SYNLAB Holding Deutschland GmbH
Germany

SYNLAB Holding Deutschland GmbH in Germany initiated a initiative to identify patients with Familial Hypercholesterolemia (FH) using clinical laboratory expertise. Individuals with FH have high premature mortality but are often undetected; early treatment significantly reduces cardiovascular risk. An FH alert screens every lipid status request. If cholesterol levels exceed thresholds in patients up to 60 years, request physicians receive an automatically generated supplementary report. This cross-industry collaboration proved effective in identifying potential high-risk patients with undetected FH.

13. Avoiding Insufficient Therapies and Overdosing with Co-Reporting eGFRs for Personalized Drug Therapy and Improved Outcomes

Marienhospital
Germany

At Marienhospital Stuttgart, Germany, an initiative was implemented to improve personalized drug therapy in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). CKD requires drug dosage adjustment based on kidney function. eGFR estimates based on creatinine can be inaccurate. Co-reporting creatinine and cystatin C provides a more accurate eGFR estimate. This identifies patients at risk of erroneous eGFR estimation, enabling optimal drug dosing, leading to improved patient outcomes, and avoiding under- or over-dosing.

14. Improving the Safety of Mothers and Babies Using Angiogenic Biomarkers for Pre-eclampsia

Clinical Biochemistry, Oxford University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust and Nuffield Department of Women's & Reproductive Health, University of Oxford
England

Oxford University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust and the University of Oxford, UK, initiated and expanded the use of angiogenic biomarkers (sFlt1 and PlGF) to improve the diagnosis and management of pre-eclampsia (PE). PE affects 4-8% of women and causes significant morbidity/mortality. Current identification methods are sub-optimal. Collaboration supported a clinical trial showing improved results. Implementing a rapid sFlt1/PlGF ratio test with a 99.3% negative predictive value for 7 days in routine care is improving safety.

15. Intelligent Liver Function Testing (iLFT): A Cost-Effective Way to Increase Early Diagnosis of Liver Disease

University of Dundee
Scotland

At the University of Dundee, UK, the Intelligent Liver Function Test (iLFT) was developed. This automated system investigates abnormal initial liver function tests requested in primary care. It uses laboratory functionality and IT systems to combine clinical data and biomarkers with expert hepatologist input. The system generates a diagnosis or management plan as a URL link. The goal is to increase early diagnosis of liver disease, improve prognosis, and reduce long-term healthcare costs.

16. Improved Diagnostic Pathway and Treatment for Hospitalized Patients with Acute Kidney Injury

Ernst von Bergmann Hospital with the Dialysis Center Potsdam and the Diaverum Kidney Care Center MVZ Potsdam affiliated with Otto-von-Guericke University Magdeburg
Germany

Diaverum Kidney Care Centre Potsdam and affiliated institutions in Germany implemented an initiative to improve diagnosis and treatment of Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) in hospitalized patients. AKI is a determinant of CKD and cardiovascular mortality, affecting ~10% of hospitalized patients, with hospital mortality of 20-25%. The initiative uses an electronic AKI alert based on serum creatinine increase and incorporates clinical practice guidelines. Leveraging universal serum creatinine screening has improved identification of previously undiagnosed AKI (about 2 out of 3 were unrecognized before).

2020

17. Strategic SARS-CoV-2 Testing for Risk Mitigation and Optimal Health of Healthcare Workers and Patients

Marienhospital
Germany

Marienhospital Stuttgart in Germany implemented rapid PCR testing for healthcare workers (HCWs) and high-risk patients, and antibody testing. Pooling strategies were used for PCR tests on low-risk patients. High-risk patients were pre-quarantined. The initiative aims to mitigate transmission risk and ensure health and safety. It enabled facilities to remain operational and reduced intra-hospital transmissions.

18. Procalcitonin: A Successful Clinical Formula for the Early Recognition and Management of Sepsis in the Emergency Department

The Princess Alexandra Hospitals NHS Trust
England

Princess Alexandra Hospitals NHS Trust in the UK implemented a new clinical pathway in the emergency department for early sepsis identification and management using Procalcitonin (PCT). The point-of-care PCT test enables rapid assessment. This led to increased detection of high-risk patients (2.4 times higher mortality rate in those not tested with PCT) and reduced unnecessary antibiotic prescriptions.

19. Optimized Detection and Management of Thyroid Dysfunction during Pregnancy for Improving Maternal and Offspring Outcomes

Hospital Virgen de la Luz
Spain

Virgen de la Luz Hospital in Spain has optimized the detection and management of thyroid dysfunction during pregnancy. Thyroid dysfunction in pregnancy is associated with increased risks for both mothers and newborns. The hospital introduced new, locally calibrated reference ranges for TSH. Prospective implementation improved the accuracy of hyperthyroidism classification, reducing patient stress and avoiding unnecessary costs.

20. Maximizing Delivery Method and Clinical Resources for Timely Patient Communication of COVID-19 Status

Nova Scotia Health
Canada

Nova Scotia Health in Canada implemented a system to communicate negative COVID-19 test results to patients via email or web link instead of by phone. Using IT and laboratory information systems, the system rapidly sent thousands of notifications. The aim was to save staff time and optimize resource use. The project saved significant staff time and accelerated the communication of negative results.

21. Maintain High Quality Patient Care during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Istitut für Medizinische und Chemische Labordiagnostik, Mein Hanusch Krankenhaus
Austria

The Institut für Medizinische und Chemische Labordiagnostik, Mein Hanusch Krankenhaus in Vienna, Austria, developed a multidisciplinary safety concept to operate safely during the COVID-19 pandemic. This included SARS-CoV-2 testing (PCR and antibodies), separate pathways for patients and healthcare workers, and access control. Operational capacity was maintained at nearly 90%. The project helped reduce uncontrolled transmission and maintain outpatient and inpatient services at nearly full capacity. Antibody screening improved the understanding of healthcare workers' immune status.

22. Laboratory-Led Company-Wide Screening Programs for Safe, Back to Work Strategies during COVID-19 Pandemic in Saudi Arabia

Dr. Suliman Al Habib Medical Group
Saudi Arabia

Dr. Suliman Al Habib Medical Group implemented a laboratory-led screening initiative to support safe return-to-work strategies for private companies across Saudi Arabia during the COVID-19 pandemic. The program involved periodic SARS-CoV-2 testing, isolation protocols, and evidence-based risk management consultancy. The initiative contributed to maintaining business continuity while mitigating workplace transmission of the virus.

23. Increased Detection of Acute Myocardial Infarction in Women Using Sex-Specific Upper Reference Limits in Clinical Pathways for Patients Presenting with Suspected Acute Coronary Syndrome

Kokilaben Dhirubhai Ambani Hospital & Medical Research Institute
India

Kokilaben Dhirubhai Ambani Hospital and Medical Research Institute in India examined sex differences in acute myocardial infarction presentation and outcomes. Women have higher mortality rates and often atypical symptoms. The project investigated the implementation of sex-specific upper reference limits for troponin. The goal is to improve detection of previously undiagnosed AMI in women and optimize treatment, reducing diagnostic delays.

24. Improving Population Health through Screening for Hepatitis C to Enable Treatment for Undetected Viral Infections

Biomédica de Referencia
Mexico

Biomédica de Referencia in Mexico City, Mexico, collaborated with the Mexican Foundation for Liver Health to improve the identification and treatment of Hepatitis C (HCV). An integrated care team supported the initiative. Barriers to identification and treatment were addressed through testing, follow-up, and public awareness campaigns. Over 70,000 individuals were screened. This led to greater detection of previously unknown HCV infections (0.3%). Early identification allows for prompt treatment, prevents disease progression, and reduces healthcare costs.

25. Improving Patient Experiences via Reliable Pre-Surgical Biomarker Risk Assessment in Patients Undergoing Eye Surgery

St. Petersburg Hospital Number Two
Russia

St. Petersburg Hospital in Russia has improved preoperative risk assessments for patients undergoing eye surgery through the use of biomarkers. Incomplete pre-surgical risk assessments, led to surgical delays, wasted resources and patient dissatisfaction. A multidisciplinary team implemented a standardized process that reduced average hospital stays and the number of repeated tests, thereby improving patient experience and satisfaction.

26. Improving Care and Overall Experience for Patients who Present to a Tanzania Clinic with Suspected Cardiovascular Diseases

Faith Medical Tanzania Clinics
Tanzania

Faith Medical Tanzania Clinics in Tanzania addressed high costs and limited resources in cardiovascular disease management. They implemented high-sensitivity troponin testing in routine clinical practice. The collaboration streamlined triage and testing to accelerate care for patients, especially when referred to other hospitals. This leads to improvements in patient treatment and outcomes through faster diagnosis.

27. Enhanced Discovery of Unidentified Comorbidities and Diagnosis through the use of Diagnostic Logics Empowered by Laboratory Medicine and Informatics

Seirei Hamamatsu HP
Japan

Seirei Hamamatsu Hospital in Japan has enhanced the detection of previously unidentified comorbidities and improved diagnostic accuracy through the use of diagnostic logic. The "Logistics Support" activity relies on the analysis of laboratory results and patient data to stratify risk and provide tailored recommendations. This approach deepens disease understanding, reduces clinical uncertainty, and optimizes healthcare costs.

28. COVID-19: Using Data, Innovation, and Collaboration to Support Better Patient Outcomes

North West London Pathology
England

North West London Pathology (NWLP) in the UK collaborated with local NHS trusts and laboratories to implement rapid PCR COVID-19 testing. They validated several methodologies and kits. The goal was to provide an effective response to the pandemic. They significantly increased testing capacity (up to 2,400 tests per day) and delivered results rapidly (24–48 hours).

29. Use of Faecal Immunochemical Tests (FIT) Unlocks the Door to Efficient and Effective Investigation of patients with New Bowel Symptoms

NHS Tayside
Scotland

NHS Tayside in Dundee, UK, integrated the Faecal Immunochemical Test (FIT) into the colorectal pathway for patients with new bowel symptoms. FIT helps distinguish high-risk from low-risk patients for colorectal cancer or other significant diseases. A low FIT result has a high negative predictive value. This reduced colonoscopy referrals by 15%, optimized investigation strategies, and improved patient management.

30. Reduction of Inpatient Daily Blood Draws with Data Science and Clinical Collaboration

St. Paul's Hospital
Canada

St. Paul's Hospital in Canada has successfully reduced unnecessary daily blood draws for inpatients. The issue stemmed from routine blood tests being ordered without specified end dates. Data analysis identified a high number of redundant tests. A new hospital policy now mandates review of test orders, resulting in a 28% reduction in repeated blood draws.

31. Reducing Post-Operative Complications in Cardiac Surgery Patients

Hospital Virgen Macarena
Spain

Virgen Macarena Hospital in Spain has reduced postoperative complications in cardiac surgery patients. Coagulopathy and postoperative bleeding are common concerns. An integrated team implemented a strategic coagulation management algorithm using viscoelastic point-of-care testing. This approach significantly reduced the need for blood transfusions and shortened intensive care unit stays.

32. Reducing Medical Errors and Enhancing Patient Care through Pathology Led Strategic Activation of Point-of-Care Testing in an Emerging Market

Aga Khan University Hospital
Kenya

At the Aga Khan University Hospital in Nairobi, Kenya, a strategy was implemented to integrate high-quality testing, including Point-of-Care Testing (POCT), into clinical care pathways. The goal was to overcome gaps in the quality and timeliness of laboratory tests in resource-limited settings. The initiative led to a radical revision of internal processes. The POCT strategy was expanded to 33 additional sites. It improved test accuracy and timeliness, optimized patient flow, and increased clinician confidence.

33. Reducing Catastrophic Adverse Events in Patients with Hemorrhagic Shock through Early Recognition of Risk and System-Wide Automatic Alerts

Hospital Israelita Albert Einstein
Brazil

Hospital Israelita Albert Einstein in São Paulo, Brazil, implemented a system for early recognition of hemorrhagic shock risk and automatic alerts. “Code Yellow” identifies the risk of decompensation, and “Code H” signals catastrophic events. These alerts trigger rapid actions, including lab testing, blood transfusions, and imaging. The protocols improved patient safety and reduced mortality, operating 24/7.

34. Novel Collaborative Approach Among Public and Private Sectors for Streamlined SARS-CoV-2 Testing Towards Optimized Patient Outcome During COVID-19 Pandemic

Dubai Health Authority
United Arab Emirates

The Dubai Health Authority (DHA) in the United Arab Emirates implemented a collaborative strategy with private laboratories to optimize SARS-CoV-2 testing. Guidelines were issued and preventive measures implemented. The focus was on increasing testing capacity and result timeliness (24–48 hours). This strategy reduced transmission, decreased community infection, hospitalization, and mortality rates.

35. Improved Safety for Patients with Indeterminant Pulmonary Nodules through Optimized Diagnostic Pathways for Lung Cancer

The First Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University
Mainland China

The First Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University in Mainland China has optimized diagnostic pathways for lung cancer in patients with indeterminate pulmonary nodules. The main challenge was assessing malignancy risk and avoiding unnecessary invasive procedures. An integrated team introduced optimized pathways and a risk model using low-dose CT (LDCT), significantly enhancing patient safety by avoiding unnecessary procedures and enabling earlier treatment.

36. Enhanced Identification and Care for Patients with Undetected HCV and/or HIV via Opt-Out ED Screening with Active Education and Linkage to Care

University of Alabama-Birmingham
USA

The University of Alabama at Birmingham (UAB) in the United States has improved the identification and care of patients with undiagnosed HCV and/or HIV through opt-out screening in the emergency department (ED). Many affected individuals are unaware of their status and lack access to care. The program implemented opt-out ED screening, coupled with education and linkage to care, leading to increased screening uptake and facilitating timely access to appropriate treatment.

37. Early Detection and Management of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus for Improved Outcomes of Mothers and their Babies

Hospital Clínico San Carlos
Spain

At Hospital Clínico San Carlos in Madrid, Spain, a multidisciplinary team focused on improving the detection and management of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM). They used early glucose tolerance tests and guideline-based recommendations. The implementation of a one-step pathway increased GDM

detection from 10.6% to 30%, leading to targeted treatment. This resulted in reduced overall direct costs and an estimated annual saving of €250,000.

38. Reducing Patient Risk and Enhancing Care through the Development and Implementation of a New Chest Pain Pathway, Expedited by and for the COVID-19 Era

Canterbury District Health Board
New Zealand

The Canterbury District Health Board in Christchurch, New Zealand, developed a new multidisciplinary pathway for patients with chest pain in emergency departments. It uses laboratory cardiac troponin results for risk stratification. Goals include minimizing ED time, reducing admissions, shortening length of stay, and reducing unnecessary tests. The risk-based pathway improves diagnosis and patient treatment, increases clinical confidence, and saves healthcare costs.

39. Kidney Check: The Next Generation of Surveillance for Hypertension, Diabetes and Chronic Kidney Disease

University of Manitoba, Chronic Disease Innovation Center at Seven Oaks General Hospital
Canada

The Chronic Disease Innovation Center at Seven Oaks General Hospital in Canada has implemented the Kidney Check program to monitor hypertension, diabetes, and chronic kidney disease. This initiative addresses the high prevalence of these conditions, particularly among Indigenous populations with limited access to care. By using point-of-care testing (POCT), the program enhances healthcare access and delivery in rural and remote Canadian communities.

40. Early Diagnosis and Improved Management of Patients with Diabetes through Strategic and Automated Test Algorithms via Primary Care

Hospital Universitari Sant Joan d'Alacant
Spain

Hospital Universitari Sant Joan d'Alacant in Spain developed an automated strategy to improve the identification of diabetes mellitus (DM), prediabetes, and the monitoring of known DM. The system, based on lab results (HbA1c, lipids, etc.), automatically generates supplemental reports and recommendations for general practitioners. This initiative improved detection and management and led to significant cost savings on tests.

2021

41. Renal Osteodystrophy Monitoring by Monthly PTH Determination in Hemodialysis CKD-MBD Patients

University Hospital Centre Zagreb & Polyclinic Avitum
Croatia

University Hospital Centre Zagreb and Polyclinic Avitum implemented monthly parathyroid hormone (PTH) monitoring for hemodialysis patients with CKD-MBD. The program optimized drug titration, preserved bone density, improved patient well-being, mitigated long-term risks, and reduced healthcare costs.

42. Optimizing the Care, Safety, and Wellness of Patients with Known Diabetes through Laboratory Medicine and a 5-stage Multidisciplinary Clinical Care Pathway

Zulekha Hospital Dubai
United Arab Emirates

Zulekha Hospital Dubai developed a five-phase clinical care pathway for known diabetic patients to address rising diabetes prevalence, complications, and associated costs. The goal was to optimize diabetic care, facilitate early diagnosis of preventable complications, improve patient engagement, reduce morbidity, and contain overall healthcare costs.

43. Improving Safety, Confidence, and Clinical Care of Cancer Patients through Screening Healthcare Workers for Neutralizing COVID-19 IgG Antibodies and Establishing a COVID-19 Convalescent Plasma Bank

King Hussein Cancer Foundation and Center
Jordan

King Hussein Cancer Foundation and Center initiated COVID-19 IgG neutralizing antibody screening for healthcare workers and established a convalescent plasma bank. This aimed to protect vulnerable oncology patients by ensuring healthcare worker immunity and providing additional therapeutic resources.

44. Improved Patient Pathway for Diagnosis, Follow-Up, and Monitoring of Multiple Myeloma (MM); a Multi-Disciplinary Collaboration to Improve the Pathway from the Initial Request to Long-Term Monitoring

Hampshire Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
England

At Hampshire Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, a multidisciplinary team redesigned the multiple myeloma diagnostic pathway by introducing an electronic test request system and IT-based algorithm. This addressed diagnostic delays and inappropriate testing, ensuring all necessary tests were done, minimizing manual work, improving response times, and reducing clinical variation.

45. Enhanced Discrimination of Myocardial Injury in a Pediatric Population Using Age-Specific Biomarker Reference Intervals

Yantai Yuhuangding Hospital
Mainland China

At Yantai Yuhuangding Hospital, a multidisciplinary team established age-specific reference intervals for hs-cTnI to replace adult-based intervals used in diagnosing pediatric myocardial injury. This improved diagnostic accuracy and discrimination, enabling better treatment and optimized use of healthcare resources.

46. Early Diagnosis of Acute Kidney Injury in Hospitalized Patients with Comorbidities

Kokilaben Dhirubhai Ambani Hospital & Medical Research Institute
India

Kokilaben Dhirubhai Ambani Hospital & Medical Research Institute developed an interdepartmental alert system for early Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) diagnosis. It aimed to help clinicians detect AKI early and initiate timely interventions, addressing the issue of late diagnosis, high complications, mortality, and costs.

47. Early Detection of Unsuspected Cardiovascular Risk in Asymptomatic Blood Donors

UOC Medicina Trasfusionale AOOR Villa-Sofia-Cervello
Italy

UOC Medicina Trasfusionale AOOR Villa-Sofia-Cervello launched a cardiovascular disease prevention initiative by testing cardiac biomarkers like hs-TnI in asymptomatic blood donors. This enabled early cardiovascular risk stratification and triggered follow-up for medium-to-high risk individuals.

48. Preventing Cardiovascular Disease in a Large Client Population through Proactive, Cost-Effective and Enhanced Identification of Cardiovascular Risk Using a Novel Laboratory Test

Medcan Health Management Inc.
Canada

In Ontario, Medcan Health Management Inc. introduced high-sensitivity troponin I (hs-cTnI) testing to replace stress tests in cardiovascular risk assessments. The goal was to improve effectiveness, reduce false positives, save time for patients and clinicians, and enable timely life-saving interventions.

49. Improving Morbidity and Mortality in Patients with Sepsis

King Abdulaziz Medical City
Saudi Arabia

King Abdulaziz Medical City - Jeddah introduced procalcitonin testing to improve sepsis diagnosis and therapy monitoring. This addressed care gaps by reducing morbidity and mortality, enabling safe early antibiotic discontinuation, and optimizing hospital stay duration.

50. Improving COVID Clinical and Translational Challenges via Multidiscipline Integrated Diagnostics Networks

UHCW NHS Trust and Warwick Medical School
England

UHCW NHS Trust and Warwick Medical School established a dedicated COVID-19 lab and integrated diagnostic networks to meet testing demand, improve turnaround times, support risk stratification and treatment, investigate transmission patterns, and contribute to the national pandemic response.

51. Sustained 97% Opt-out HIV Testing in the Emergency Department: Getting to Zero AIDS

Croydon University Hospital
England

At Croydon University Hospital, an HIV opt-out testing program was implemented in the emergency department to tackle high prevalence and late HIV diagnoses. The initiative increased early detection, reduced late diagnoses, complications, mortality, and transmission rates.

52. Enhancing Personalized Care for Heart Failure Patients: A Risk-Scoring EMR Model

Prisma Health Greenville Memorial Hospital
USA

Prisma Health Greenville Memorial Hospital created a multidisciplinary heart failure identification and management program, integrating a risk scoring system into the electronic medical record. This targeted early patient identification, improved resource access, reduced costs, optimized care coordination, and lowered mortality and hospital stays.

53. Utilizing an Innovative Approach to Process Improvement in the Era of a Global Pandemic and The Great Resignation: Rapidly Improving Timeliness of Laboratory Test Results for Multidisciplinary Rounds in an Acute Care Setting

Banner Health and Laboratory Sciences of Arizona
USA

Banner Health and Laboratory Sciences of Arizona implemented a rapid process improvement approach to address increased test volumes and staffing shortages during the pandemic and "Great Resignation." The main goal was to improve the turnaround time of routine morning lab tests essential for multidisciplinary rounds, supporting clinical decision-making and discharge planning.

2022

54. Improving Emergency Department Flow and Decreasing Risk through Development and Implementation of Molecular Diagnostics Guided Triage

Clinical Hospital Center Rijeka
Croatia

The Clinical Hospital Center Rijeka, Croatia, faced the need for rapid and accurate diagnosis in the emergency department (ED), especially for infectious diseases such as COVID-19, with long waiting times for test results. They optimized a commercial qPCR test for point-of-care use (POC-dqPCR) in the ED. This dramatically reduced turnaround times (from a maximum of 44 to 6 hours), improving clinical decision-making and reducing the risk of transmission.

55. Improved and Accelerated Diagnostic Pathway for Patients that Present to the Emergency Department with Suspected Mild Traumatic Brain Injury

Hospital Universitario Virgen de las Nieves
Spain

Hospital Universitario Virgen de las Nieves, Spain, aimed to improve and accelerate the diagnostic pathway for patients with suspected mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI) presenting to the emergency department. The widespread use of CT, the gold standard, posed radiation risks and resource burdens for mild cases. They implemented a new testing panel (GFAP, UCH-L1) used alongside clinical information to guide CT decisions. This led to a reduction in unnecessary CT scans and better resource utilization.

56. Enhancing Resource Utilization and Improving Patient Experience through Strategic Laboratory Stewardship

Ain-Shams University - Emergency Hospital
Egypt

The Emergency Hospital at Ain Shams University tackled overcrowding in the emergency department, which caused delays and high costs, partly due to inappropriate lab tests. They designed a new approach to urgent testing with evidence-based panels and cross-functional consensus. This improved workflow and patient experience, allowing for faster management and the ability to treat more patients.

57. Enhanced Staff Satisfaction and Resource Utilization during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Associação Fundo de Incentivo a Pesquisa
Brazil

The Associação Fundo de Incentivo à Pesquisa (AFIP) in Brazil addressed the uncertainties and risks of COVID-19 for employees and their families, including difficulty in accessing diagnostics. They implemented a new health program based on the pre-existing CQC, with a multidisciplinary team. The program offered rapid RT-PCR testing and mental health services. This improved access to testing with new collection sites and enabled proactive quarantine and isolation.

58. A Noninvasive Serologic Model Using an Intelligent Informatic Solution to Enhance Clinical Decision-Making and Improve Patient Safety

The Second Norman Bethune Hospital of Jilin University
Mainland China

The Second Norman Bethune Hospital of Jilin University, Mainland China, aimed to improve the identification and early diagnosis of primary liver cancer (HCC), given its high incidence and low survival rate in Mainland China. Methods like ultrasound and AFP have limitations. They implemented the ASAP risk model (based on age, sex, AFP, and PIVKA-II) through a new diagnostic pathway with a digital solution. This enhanced patient safety and reduced unnecessary invasive exams.

59. Getting to Zero Harm in Controlled Substance Prescribing: Increasing the Accuracy of Prescription Compliance Monitoring through Enhanced Drug Testing Support

University Hospitals Cleveland
USA

University Hospitals Cleveland addressed the opioid overdose epidemic and the need to ensure safe prescribing of controlled substances by improving monitoring accuracy through drug testing. An interdisciplinary team designed inclusive drug testing panels, with integrated reflex testing and educational materials. The initiative increased compliance with monitoring and physician confidence, while reducing patient costs and improving convenience.

60. Enhanced Resource Utilization, Reduced Waste, and Expedited Transplantation through Real-Time Donor Screening for Infectious Disease

Mid America Transplant St. Louis, Missouri
USA

Mid America Transplant in the USA identified inefficiencies in the donor screening process for infectious diseases, which involved lengthy procedures with manual methods and resulted in recovering tissues from ineligible donors. They implemented a fully automated serological testing platform for real-time

screening. This solution improved workflow efficiency (94.7%) and reduced turnaround time, allowing tissue recovery only from eligible donors.

61. Early Diagnosis of Maternal Cytomegalovirus for Improved Management and Reduced Risk of Fetal Transmission and Complications

National Reference Center for Herpesvirus, University Hospital Center
France

The National Reference Center for Herpesvirus in Limoges, France, focused on congenital cytomegalovirus (cCMV), the leading non-genetic cause of hearing loss and neurodevelopmental disabilities in children. Despite the risks, diagnosis is complex, and there is no universal screening during pregnancy. They adopted a universal CMV screening program for pregnant women. This increased infection identification (2.6 times) and supported early neonatal management with antiviral therapy.

62. The “Bubble”: Safe and Informed Population Health Management Based on Strategic, Novel Laboratory Testing to Restart a Global Sports League, Stimulate the Economy, and Foster Normalcy During the COVID-19 Pandemic

National Basketball Association
USA

The National Basketball Association (NBA) faced the challenge of safely restarting the season during the COVID-19 pandemic. They created the "NBA Bubble", an occupational health program in a closed campus. The program included comprehensive testing strategies (daily PCR tests), quarantine measures, and strict infection control protocols. This enabled the season to proceed safely with zero cases among resident players and staff, protecting revenue and preserving jobs.

63. Program ROSE (Removing Obstacles to Cervical ScRееning) - Empowering Women to Eliminate Cervical Cancer

ROSE Foundation
Malaysia

The ROSE Foundation in Malaysia addressed the high incidence of cervical cancer in the country and low participation in traditional screenings (Pap tests) due to discomfort and long waiting times. They launched the ROSE Program, based on HPV screening with self-sampling and digital technology. This woman-centered approach, with rapid results and digital navigation, significantly increased participation and follow-up care for women who tested positive for HPV, enabling early intervention and improved wellness.

64. Improving the Peri-Operative Pathway of People with Diabetes Undergoing Elective Surgery: The IP3D Project

Ipswich Hospital, East Suffolk and North Essex NHS
England

Ipswich Hospital in the UK addressed the difficulties and risks for diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery, who experienced postoperative complications and prolonged length of stay. They introduced the IP3D project (Improving the Perioperative Pathway of People with Diabetes). This included a portable tool for patients, a dedicated working group, and the hiring of a specialist nurse. The initiative led to a reduction in complications and average length of stay.

2024

65. The Women and Heart Program - Empowering Women's Health through Early Identification and Prevention of Coronary Risk

Institute for Cardiovascular Prevention and Rehabilitation
Croatia

The Institute for Cardiovascular Prevention and Rehabilitation in Croatia addressed the high cardiovascular mortality rate, particularly among post-menopausal women. The “Women and Heart” program screened women over 45 using a biomarker panel—including hs-TnI—to assess CVD risk. In the first year, over 1,000 healthy women were screened, with 10.9% identified as moderate/high risk for follow-up.

66. Reducing Unnecessary CT Scans in the Emergency Department with New Mild Head Injury Assessment Pathway

Klinikum Lüneburg
Germany

Klinikum Lüneburg in Germany reduced unnecessary CT scans in patients with mild traumatic brain injury (TBI) in the emergency department. Previously reliant on clinical judgment, a new protocol incorporated a blood test measuring GFAP and UCH-L1 to objectively rule out intracranial injury in patients with GCS scores of 13–15 within 12 hours of injury. This reduced CT usage by 41%.

67. Reducing Unnecessary Admissions Associated with Pediatric Mononucleosis via Implementation of EBV IgM Testing in the Emergency Department

Emergency Clinical County Hospital Târgu Mureş
Romania

The Emergency Clinical County Hospital Târgu Mureş in Romania reduced unnecessary hospital admissions and waiting times for pediatric patients with suspected mononucleosis. Previously, many children were admitted for tests requiring several days. By incorporating EBV IgM testing into the pediatric emergency panel, clinicians enabled faster exclusion or discharge. This led to a 2% reduction in referrals/admissions and a substantial decrease in diagnostic waiting times.

68. The Kansas Two-Step: Simplifying the Diagnosis of Clostridioides Difficile at an Academic Medical Center

The University of Kansas Health System
USA

The University of Kansas Health System in the USA simplified Clostridioides difficile (C. diff) diagnosis, addressing inflated reportable rates due to the inability to distinguish infection from colonization. A two-step testing algorithm (PCR followed by toxin EIA) was introduced, leading to a 76% decrease in reportable cases, a 25% reduction in inappropriate antibiotic use, and \$4.3 million in savings.

69. No Time to Lose with Lives on the Line - Maximizing Efficiency in the Lab to Save More Lives through Organ Donation

Southwest Transplant Alliance
USA

The Southwest Transplant Alliance in the USA accelerated infectious disease screening for organ donors to increase transplantation opportunities, particularly in urgent cases. Previously, delays were caused by combining organ donor testing with slower tissue/eye donor procedures. A separate fast-track testing pathway was implemented for organ donors, improving resource utilization, reducing costs, and saving more lives.

70. Establishment of a Monomer Prolactin Detection Method and Specific Reference Interval to Enhance the Ability to Identify Macroprolactinemia

Huashan Hospital Fudan University
Mainland China

Huashan Hospital Fudan University in Mainland China improved the identification of macroprolactinemia, a condition that can lead to misdiagnosis of hyperprolactinemia due to assay interference. The hospital established a screening protocol using polyethylene glycol precipitation and a method for monomeric prolactin detection. Among 14,950 tested patients, 3,238 were diagnosed with macroprolactinemia, reducing unnecessary medications, imaging, anxiety, and costs.

71. Improving Equity in Maternal and Newborn Outcomes by Eliminating Disparities in Maternal Drug Screening

Washington University School of Medicine, Barnes-Jewish Hospital, and St. Louis Children's Hospital
USA

The Washington University School of Medicine in the USA eliminated racial disparities in maternal drug screening, where Black mothers were disproportionately tested and reported for isolated cannabis use. A

multidisciplinary team revised hospital policies to remove isolated cannabis use as a testing criterion, facilitated by EMR system updates. This resulted in a 75% reduction in testing and the elimination of racial disparity.

72. Improving Access to Health Services in Vulnerable Communities Affected by War

Esculab
Ukraine

Esculab in Ukraine responded to the war's impact on the healthcare system, which left millions without access to essential and preventive care. Esculab Medical Laboratory launched social initiatives providing free standard diagnostic tests (e.g., glucose, lipid profile) to vulnerable individuals. More than 90,000 people received free testing, emphasizing the role of prevention even during wartime.

73. Improved Patient Outcomes Facilitated by C-peptide Testing, Enabling Reclassification and Therapeutic Changes for Patients with Diabetes

University Hospital of Wales
Wales

The University Hospital of Wales in the UK re-evaluated patients previously classified as having type 1 diabetes (T1DM) to improve diagnosis and treatment. Using C-peptide testing as a marker of insulin reserve, the hospital identified patients eligible for reclassification as type 2 or monogenic diabetes. Treatment adjustments, including insulin discontinuation for 5.2% of patients, led to improved glycemic control, BMI, and quality of life, alongside significant cost savings.

74. Improved Management of Patients with High LDL-C through Electronic Health Record-Directed Algorithms for Guideline-Concordant High-Intensity Statin Prescribing

Kaiser Permanente Southern California
USA

Kaiser Permanente Southern California in the USA enhanced the management of patients with elevated low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), where high-intensity statins are under-prescribed. The SureNet program utilized algorithms on electronic health records to identify patients and automatically generate statin prescriptions and follow-up test orders. This led to a 36% increase in statin prescriptions, a 32% improvement in medication pick-up, and a 41% rise in test completion, ultimately reducing LDL-C in 21% of patients.

75. GetCheckedOnline: Better Access to Testing for Sexually-Transmitted and Blood-Borne Infections

British Columbia Centre for Disease Control
Canada

The BC Centre for Disease Control in Canada launched GetCheckedOnline (GCO), a digital public health initiative designed to overcome barriers to screening for sexually and blood-borne infections (STBBIs). The online platform enables users to generate lab requisitions and access partner testing sites, with test recommendations based on an online risk assessment. GCO improved accessibility, reached at-risk populations, and reduced strain on healthcare services.

76. Early Detection of Metabolic-Dysfunction Associated Steatotic Liver Disease Using FIB-4

Premier Integrated Labs Sdn Bhd
Malaysia

Premier Integrated Labs Sdn Bhd in Malaysia addressed the silent epidemic of MASLD, which is often asymptomatic, by implementing FIB-4 scoring—a tool using readily available parameters to assess liver fibrosis. Among 39,020 patients screened, 5,662 were identified as being at moderate or high risk. This approach enhanced patient outcomes, supported clinical decision-making, and reduced overall healthcare costs.

2025

77. Enhancing Wellness through Guideline Concordant Follow-Up and Treatment for Patients with Diabetes and Chronic Kidney Disease

National Kidney Foundation in collaboration with Sanford Health
USA

The National Kidney Foundation (NKF) and Sanford Health partnered to enhance care for diabetic patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), identifying gaps in testing and diagnosis. They implemented a system-level intervention aligned with NKF recommendations, including specific lab tests, EHR updates, and educational resources. Within the first 10 months, the proportion of diabetic patients receiving guideline-concordant CKD testing increased from 38% to 70%. This contributed to a 53% increase in newly documented CKD diagnoses in the EHR.

78. Personalizing H. Pylori Antibiotic Therapy for Enhanced Safety and H. Pylori Eradication

University Hospitals Cleveland
USA

University Hospitals addressed increasing antibiotic resistance in H. pylori by developing a molecular assay to detect resistance mutations. The test was integrated into routine clinical practice, enabling personalized treatment recommendations. Pharmacists directly communicated test results to physicians. This approach improved H. pylori eradication rates by over 17% for first-line therapy and reduced inappropriate treatments by 30%, also decreasing clarithromycin resistance.

79. Improved Patient Experiences and Decreased Patient Length of Stay in the Emergency Department through a Multidisciplinary Approach

Banner Health and Laboratory Sciences of Arizona
USA

Banner Health and Laboratory Sciences of Arizona launched a multidisciplinary initiative to reduce emergency department length of stay (ED LOS). Applying DMAI3C and Lean principles, they implemented direct patient bedding and established dedicated phlebotomy areas. These collaborative efforts led to a 20.2% reduction in patient LOS, driven by improvements in lab draw times (23.3% reduction), door-to-provider times (70.4% improvement), and imaging efficiency (17.5% improvement). The initiative also reduced by 65% the number of patients leaving the ED without being seen.

80. Reduced Hepatocellular Carcinoma Recurrence with Enhanced 3-Year Survival for Patients Post Liver Transplant

Kaohsiung Chang Gung Memorial Hospital
Taiwan

Kaohsiung Chang Gung Memorial Hospital developed an innovative approach for locally advanced hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) by using AFP and PET imaging to predict post-transplant recurrence and implementing pre-transplant therapies (TARE/proton therapy) for downstaging. Among 43 patients treated, 24 were successfully downstaged and subsequently transplanted. These patients exhibited a significantly reduced 3-year recurrence rate (8.3% vs. 35.2%) and improved overall survival (85.9% vs. 69.3%) compared to historical data or non-transplanted patients.

81. Implementation of a Comprehensive Syphilis Screening Strategy for Cost-Effective and Timely Syphilis Management

Tongji Hospital, Tongji Medical College, Huazhong University of Science and Technology
Mainland China

Tongji Hospital addressed the rising incidence of syphilis in Mainland China and associated diagnostic delays by implementing a comprehensive syphilis screening strategy, which included immediate reflex testing and revised diagnostic thresholds for neonates and children. This initiative significantly improved diagnostic accuracy, reduced the number of visits required for diagnosis by 67%, and identified syphilis in 14.9% of initially screening-negative patients. Estimated healthcare savings ranged from RMB 2,100 to RMB 4,300 per patient.

82. The Fiix Project: Reducing Anticoagulation Variability and Adverse Patient Outcomes through Safe and Cost-Effective Factor II and X (Fiix) Monitoring in Place of Conventional PT-INR Warfarin Monitoring

Landspítali National University Hospital of Iceland
Landspítali National University Hospital of Iceland
Iceland

The Landspítali National University Hospital of Iceland aimed to improve warfarin management, recognizing the limitations of conventional PT-INR monitoring. They implemented a novel monitoring test, Fiix-PT, which is sensitive only to reductions in coagulation factors FII and FX. Findings indicate that Fiix-NR monitoring reduced anticoagulation variability by 33% and lowered thromboembolic complications by 40–56%, without increasing major bleeding events. The approach proved more efficient, requiring fewer tests and allowing longer monitoring intervals.

83. TBI Strategies: Expediting Patient Flow and Reducing Length of Stay through Blood Biomarker Guided Management of Patients with Suspected Mild Traumatic Brain Injury

Centre Hospitalier Universitaire of Clermont-Ferrand
France

The Centre Hospitalier Universitaire of Clermont-Ferrand addressed the management of mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI), which accounts for 80% of all TBIs in France. They implemented the S100B blood biomarker in the ED to help rule-out the need for a CT scan, which are often negative for patients with mTBI. This collaborative effort led to an average reduction of 3 hours and 35 minutes in ED length of stay for patients with suspected mTBI. The initiative also saved approximately 2,300 hours of clinical and non-clinical staff time annually, and €5,184 in healthcare costs due to 216 avoided CT scans. Notably, 82% of clinicians adhered strictly to the S100B protocol.

84. The Pathway to HCV Elimination: Multidisciplinary Team Effort for Improved Identification, Diagnosis and Treatment of HCV Positive Patients

Musashino Red Cross Hospital
Japan

Musashino Red Cross Hospital pursued the elimination of hepatitis C virus (HCV), targeting the 1.0–1.5 million individuals in Japan with undiagnosed or untreated infections. They developed a multidisciplinary initiative combining an existing alert system with new follow-up procedures to link HCV antibody-positive patients to care. The project resulted in a 33.7% reduction in missed referrals for HCV-positive patients and facilitated treatment initiation in 8.3% of untreated or unlinked known positives. This initiative prevented an estimated ¥46.4 million in annual chemotherapy costs for avoidable liver cancer cases.

85. Radiation Reduction: Increased Safety and Improved Length of Stay for Patients with Suspected Mild Traumatic Brain Injury in the Emergency Department

Complejo Hospitalario Universitario Nuestra Señora de Candelaria
Spain

The Hospital Universitario Nuestra Señora de Candelaria enhanced the evaluation of mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI) in emergency departments by introducing a novel blood test based on the biomarkers GFAP and UCHL-1, aimed at reducing unnecessary CT scans. This innovation enabled 36.8% of mTBI patients to avoid CT imaging, thereby decreasing radiation exposure. It also shortened the average emergency department (ED) stay by 4.2 hours, improving patient flow. The approach alleviated 4,490 hours of radiologists' time and generated annual healthcare savings of approximately €274,000. Physicians reported increased confidence and satisfaction in managing mTBI cases.

AHEAD

The AHEAD series was conceived as a vehicle for disseminating the research carried out within the CRC in Health Administration (HEAD).

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